

ECONOMY OF CARE AND HUMAN RIGHTS: THE ARGENTINE DECREE 475/2021

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to investigate to what extent the Argentine Decree 475/2021, which recognizes maternal care as a contribution time for retirement, favors the insertion of Care Economics as a practice of human rights promotion and defense within the scope of Feminist Economics. This theoretical-empirical research uses the conceptual framework of Feminist Economics, qualitatively approached to classify the Argentine case according to its relevance for the entering of the gender topic in the global human rights agenda. Primary and secondary sources were consulted for analytical-descriptive purposes and lead us to consider that the aforementioned Decree constitutes a contribution in line with the Feminist Conciliation Economy. Contributions concerning the inclusion of a feminist perspective in public policies to mitigate economic gender disparities. Despite not presenting a priori effective breaks with the market logic and androcentric precepts of traditional economics, it was influenced by the context of political praxis and demands of the international feminist movement and the Argentine struggle for women's rights.

Keywords: Care economics; Feminist economics; Human rights; gender equality; Argentina.

INITIAL CONSIDERATIONS

On July 17, 2021, Argentina published Decree 475/2021, which recognizes maternal care as a period of service that can be counted towards retirement (ARGENTINA, 2021). Under the new rules, women will be able to add up to three years of service time, per child born alive, to reach social security contribution time. Recognizing the contribution of feminist movements in the country as a significant backdrop, this paper aims to investigate to what extent the Argentine case favors the insertion of the Care Economy as a Human Rights practice within the scope of the growing debate on Feminist Economics.

Feminist Economics seeks to expand the object of study of economics, arguing that it is not just productive work (that visible in the market, in remunerated exchanges, in the public

sphere), which must be investigated by economics. Defends the existence of reproductive work (care, domestic sphere), questioning its invisibility. It questions why, even though it is useful to capitalism, these aspects are not visible, accounted for (NELSON, 1995; FERNANDES, 2018; TEIXEIRA, 2018). It is argued that this is because traditional economics was knowledge created by men to explain the experiences of the world from an androcentric, typically male, perspective (PÉREZ OROZCO, 2005).

What is socially called masculine and feminine, or what is said to be the responsibility of women or men, is strictly related to a cultural and social construction that is reflected in all spheres of human life, including work; the term coined for the construct when applied in this environment is the sexual division of labor:

The sexual division of labor is the form of division of social labor resulting from social relations of sex; its characteristics are the priority allocation of men to the productive sphere and women to the reproductive sphere and, simultaneously, the occupation by men of functions with a strong added social value (political, religious, military, etc.). This form of social vision of work has two organizing principles: that of separation (there are jobs for men and others for women) and that of hierarchization (a job for a man is “worth” more than one for a woman) (KERGOAT, 2009, p. . 67).

Therefore, the sexual division of labor determined women to care for family members (children, the elderly and the disabled), household chores (GOIS, 2017). However, it is common for women dedicated to housework and raising children not to participate in the distribution of economic resources. Silvia Federici, while criticizing such exclusionary system, offers contributions that provoke reflection: “There is a big difference between making chairs, shoes or cars, and the work of making children, of raising children [...] We are the factories of workers. From food to clothing and emotional labor. [...] What they call love, we call unpaid work.” (PASSOS, 2019, np).

Within the scope of Feminist Economics, the concept of the Care Economy sheds light on this agenda. Researcher Esquivel (2011), in a report by the United Nations Development Program, characterized the Care Economy as a concept derived from the debate on domestic work that began in the 1970s, highlighting women's work linked to satisfying the basic needs of individuals. of the domestic environment, especially children and the elderly, a task carried out beyond the mercantile sphere and invisible to conventional economic statistics and remuneration purposes. Marçal (2017) uses Beauvoir's (2008) feminist description of women as the “second sex” to exemplify the economic logic of the Care Economy:

Just as there is a 'second sex' there is a 'second economy'. The work traditionally done by men is what counts. It defines the economic worldview. The woman's work is 'the other'. It's everything he doesn't do, but depends on to be able to do what he does. (MARÇAL, 2017, p. 26).

The unequal conditions faced by women in society, which characterize major human rights violations, are historical and the current pandemic context has reinforced such evidence. The Covid-19 pandemic generated a health crisis, already prolonged for 2 years, which was responsible for the closure of institutions such as schools, among other care institutions, which forced women to take on even greater loads of domestic work. Due to the isolation and reduced contact imputed to those responsible for the care and the prioritization of relationships that stick to the physical limits of the home, the burden of care and domestic work is perceived intrinsically to the conditions in which women are inserted, as described in the report “Untying the crisis” (TRICONTINENTAL, 2021).

At the end of 2020, the Social Panorama of Latin America, produced annually by the Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean, recorded 209 million people at the poverty level (ECLAC, 2021), meaning an increase of 22 million individuals in a situation of economic vulnerability and levels that were not observed in the last 12 and 20 years, respectively. In addition to presenting the rise of an economic crisis caused by the Covid-19 pandemic in the region, they demonstrate how this factor was responsible for higher inequality rates and lower occupation rates in the labor market, especially by female individuals, whose percentage of labor participation was 46% in 2020, while that of males totaled 69% (ECLAC, 2021).

This theoretical-empirical work uses the conceptual framework of Feminist Economics to, through a qualitative approach, classify the Argentine case according to its degree of rupture with androcentrism and analyze its contributions to the gender agenda in the context of the human rights agenda. Primary (Decree 475/2021) and secondary sources (bibliography and reports) were consulted with analytical-descriptive purposes.

The text is divided into four parts: the first defines the precepts of the Care Economy; the second presents the Argentine Decree; the third contextualizes Argentine feminist movements as one of its main catalysts; so that, finally, the categories of the Feminist and Gender Economy debate are presented that allow analysis on the alignment of the current Decree with the gender agenda in Human Rights.

Care Economy

The Care Economy is a proposal created in the context of feminist economics, which defends the visibility and recognition of activities performed in an unpaid manner and primarily by women, who do not acquire the status of an economic category (CARRASCO et al, 2011 apud ESQUIVEL, 2011). The studies gathered under the scope of the economy of care are based on the assumption that unpaid care is not only part of the economic system, but is also a precondition for its existence. Based on this understanding, they seek to measure and value care work; to ascertain the working conditions and remuneration of occupations related to care and social reproduction; point to the nature of the relationships between the subjects involved in their performance; and examine the position of those who perform it in the labor market (ESQUIVEL, 2011, p. 16). In general, the concept still raises doubts, as they understand that it is related to the profession of caregivers, when in fact:

Care economy is a term that designates the work, mostly carried out by women, dedicated to the survival, well-being and/or education of people, as well as to the maintenance of the environment in that are inserted. In the domestic sphere, this work is invisible and unpaid. In the professional environment - outsourced -, he is poorly paid (MENA, 2020, np).

Care Economy studies also shed light on the inequality suffered by women in the work environment, both in terms of salary, with the recognition of this disparity not being enough to mitigate discrimination (SOARES, 2010 apud TEIXEIRA, 2018), since factors as the absence of women on maternity leave also constitute one of the conservative arguments for female labor exclusion and devaluation (TEIXEIRA, 2018).

Theorists of the Care Economy, therefore, warn of the need to develop public policies and actions that prevent family responsibilities typically attributed to women from serving as an obstacle to training or employment, reducing the workload of family care through socialization and guaranteeing the right of children and adolescents to receive care not only in the context of their community and family, but also in institutional contexts through comprehensive policies, as proposed by the Interministerial Board of Care Policies (2020, p. 22).

From this concept, it is observed that the Argentine Decree proposes this economic understanding, since it creates a mechanism that considers maternal care as work, converting

part of the time of exclusion from the formal market, into accounting time for retirement. The initiative recognizes work considered invisible in neoclassical economics.

THE ARGENTINE DECREE

The *Time to Care* report, published by Oxfam (2020), estimates that at least 12.5 billion hours a day are devoted to domestic work worldwide by women over 15 years old, a job that adds an estimated US\$10.8 trillion to the economy and even so, it is carried out free of charge and mostly by women belonging to the most disadvantaged social strata.

It is by recognizing these indicators that Decree 475/2021 approved in July 2021, which amends Law 24,241 on Retirement and Pensions deserves to be studied (ARGENTINA, 2021). This instrument was created in order to combat late retirement, an effect of inequality in the labor market, which one of the reasons given is the excessive workload concentrated disproportionately on female individuals.

The so-called *Comprehensive Program for Recognition of Length of Service for Assistance Tasks* is aimed at women of retirement age – 60 years or older –, and who have not reached the minimum of 30 years of contribution required. It is noteworthy that, until then, only one out of ten Argentine women in this age group had enough time to retire (ARGENTINAS, 2021) and, with the decree, it is estimated to contemplate 155 thousand women (IBDFAM, 2021).

The modification, which is now called Retirement for Care, allows adding to the contribution time one year for each child and contemplates special cases. In general, special cases are related to: adoption of underage children or adolescents, for which two years are added per child; two years added in cases of children with disabilities; and three years for women who have benefited from the Universal Child Allowance for Protection - a government program aimed at low-income families. The modification also covers professionals with a formal contract who obtained maternity leave, with the time off starting to count as length of service (ARGENTINA, 2021) (Table 1).

QUADRO 1 - TEMPO PERMITIDO À SOMA PARA A APOSENTADORIA POR CUIDADO

Regra	Tempo Somado
Regra Geral	01 ano por cada filho
Casos Especiais - adoção de crianças ou adolescentes menores	02 anos por filho
Casos Especiais - filhos portadores de deficiências	02 anos por filho
Casos Especiais - beneficiárias do Programa Abono Universal por Filho para Proteção	03 anos

Fonte: Elaborado pela pós-graduanda, com base no texto do Decreto 475/2021.

The recognition of maternal care is a historical struggle of feminist movements, since the care that mothers need to direct to their children often makes it impossible for them to be present in other spaces. In the Argentine case:

Around 44% of women of retirement age did not have access to the benefit, either due to dismissal after maternity leave or reintegration into the labor market. Thus, 300,000 women, aged between 59 and 64, were out of retirement because they did not have the 30 years of service required as a contribution, a condition that the program promises to remedy. (CARTA CAPITAL, 2021, np).

The benefit, put into effect during the Covid-19 health crisis, is the first initiative in Argentina that recognizes the importance of care for the economy. The pandemic, despite not having been a decisive factor in the enactment of the Argentine decree, acted as an important catalyst for public policy, in a context in which a quarter of women under thirty were unemployed versus 17% of men, and the gender gap quadrupled in unemployment rates after the advance of the pandemic, according to a report produced by the Federal Bureau of Economic Policies with a Gender Perspective (2021).

The formulation of the change in the law originated in the Interministerial Table of Care Policies (2021) of Argentina; This Board is made up of 15 bodies of the National Executive Power (including Ministries, Agencies and the National Council for the Coordination of Social Policies) whose objective is to debate and plan policies that contribute to a fairer social organization, greater equality of gender and that recognize care as a need, work and right.

The Decree has its South American precedents in Chile (2008) and Uruguay (2015), respectively in the child bonus for women and in the National Integrated Care System (SNIC). It also promoted the return of the debate in the Brazilian political scenario, with a proposal made by Federal Deputy Talíria Petrone (PSOL-RJ) in the Chamber of Deputies, in August

2021, regarding the granting of a minimum wage for women over 60 and with children who have not reached the 15 years of contribution required for retirement (MENA, 2021).

It is noteworthy that this policy represents the commitment of the aforementioned Interministerial Board to the promotion of public care policies. A document from the Bureau itself informs:

Contemporary society calls us to a new pact that highlights the centrality of care as a key dimension of social well-being. The demand for a fairer organization around care tasks in an egalitarian key was consolidated from the struggles that the feminist field has been waging, and represents the maturation of a public debate that has managed to install the problem on the institutional agenda and politics. The creation of the Ministerio de las Mujeres, Genders and Diversity within the current management of the national government constitutes a signal that accounts for the listening of this demand in search of gender equality and equity. [...] The current context of the health emergency caused by COVID-19 adds up to greater challenges and responsibilities as a National State. This combination highlights the essence of care in our lives and the importance of having public policies in this area. It is clear that, if the organization of care constitutes a vector for the reproduction of inequality for women in particular, but also for LGBTI+ people, the pandemic deepens this situation, especially for the popular sectors. (ARGENTINA, 2020, p. 2 - 3, emphasis added).

By recognizing maternal care as work for retirement, it contributes to shed light on theoretical debates proposed in the context of Feminist Economics, which criticizes the androcentric bias of most current indicators. The following topic contextualizes the Argentine feminist movement and its contemporary contributions to other forms of organization in society.

WOMEN'S RIGHTS IN ARGENTINA - HISTORICAL MILESTONES

Understanding the dynamics of feminist organization and political action in Argentina is essential to contextualize the scenario of struggles and claims in favor of women's rights, which contributed to the foundations for the Decree of Retirement by Care to be enacted. Argentine feminism is characterized by Barrancos (2014) as composed of small groups and possessing a fragmented structure that spills over into multiple forms, in more popular expressions. For Aguiar and Rojas (2020), the Argentine women's movement has offered significant contributions in the struggle for human and social rights, criticizing patriarchy and its relationship with capitalism, proposing elements for the construction of another form of organization in society.

The claim for women's rights in Argentina dates back to the 1900s, with the beginning of the influence and public opinion of female individuals on politics, although their right to citizenship was far from being conquered. Feminists at the time focused on different strands, but they had four fundamental demands in common: the removal of civil inferiority, obtaining an education, assistance to needy mothers and claiming citizenship through suffrage, the last premise being widely discussed in Primer Women's Congress, in 1910, and partially conquered in 1932, when the women's vote was approved by Congress, but there was no discussion of the agenda in the Senate. This demand was only fully contemplated in 1947, when Eva Perón, who did not declare herself a feminist, mobilized women – especially through unions – against treatment in Congress, winning the sanction of suffrage (BARRANCOS, 2014).

From 1976 to 1983, Argentina lived a rigid dictatorship, giving rise to the Mothers of Plaza de Mayo movement, women who demanded the appearance of their relatives alive, victims of military repression. Aguiar and Rojas (2020) state that it can be defined as a human rights movement, central to the fight against the aforementioned military dictatorship and the demand for the punishment of the military and civilians responsible for crimes. The authors also highlight the parallel movement, called Avós da Praça de Mayo, whose objective is to find the children of political detainees-disappeared. Barrancos (2014) argues that the reopening of parliament established an institutional instance in which feminist claims were channeled, many of them resignified by the conditions of the dictatorship. In this context, Argentina became the first country to enact quotas for women's participation in the electoral sphere and served as an example for the insertion of similar norms in the legislation of twelve other countries in Latin America. The increased presence of women in the legislative sphere has allowed a greater number of laws directly or relatively linked to their well-being to be enacted.

The National Meeting of Women has been held in Argentina every year since 1986. It is a forum where women from different social strata and organizations meet to discuss political actions to be implemented in their respective spheres. From this movement, in the meetings of 2003 and 2004, arose the proposal about the unified campaign for the legalization of abortion, the National Campaign for the Right to Legal, Safe and Free Abortion. Since 2007, six legislative projects have been presented to the Chamber of Deputies of Argentina, being approved in 2018, but later overturned in the Senate (TOGNOLA, 2021).

As Aguiar and Rojas (2020) suggest, a new, more current dimension of the women's movement has been crystallizing political expression. With the outstanding motto *Ni Una a Menos*, the movement created in 2015, fights in favor of the lives of all who recognize themselves as women. It gave visibility to sexist violence by calling for marches on behalf of

victims of femicide in Argentina, such as Chiara Páez, Melina Romero, Daiana García and Micaela Ortega (EL PAÍS, 2016); marks a new moment in defining public struggle agendas being put into action on the street, leading more than 150,000 Argentines to the march (CLARÍN, 2015) and mobilizing people around the world on social media through hashtags, representing a turning point essential for the approval of the Law on Voluntary Interruption of Pregnancy to materialize (AGUIAR; ROJAS, 2020; ARGENTINA, 2021b).

It was in October 2016 that the first national women's strike took place, organized in parallel with several countries in Latin America and in various parts of the world (AGUIAR; ROJAS, 2020). The *Paro Internacional de Mujeres (PIM)* – linked to the organization *Ni Una Menos* and with the support of more than 50 organizations, parties and unions (PÚBLICO, 2016, 2017) occurred with the suspension of activities by 70,000 Argentine women due to the brutal femicide of Lucía Pérez, aged 16, in the Argentine capital, and subsequent march from the Obelisk to Plaza de Mayo in Buenos Aires; and the adherence of organizations from countries in South America, Europe and Oceania. PIM used the hashtag *#NosotrasParamos* to call not only Argentine women, but women from more than 30 countries to propose a total or partial stoppage of their work, consumption or domestic activities to draw attention to the fight against violence sexism, wage inequality and the right to abortion (PÚBLICO, 2017). Since then, the call for strikes has been held every March 8 worldwide (GAGO, 2020).

In Argentina, half a million women were mobilized in each of the marches that joined the strikes of October 2016 and March 2017; eight hundred thousand in March 2018 and a similar number in March 2019, after even more massive mobilizations in 2018 demanding the decriminalization of abortion (GAGO, 2020). According to Gago (2021, np) “The strike produced a leap: it transformed the mobilization against femicides into a radical, massive movement capable of linking and politicizing the rejection of violence in an innovative way. The strike, however, brought to the fore an accumulated history of previous struggles.”.

According to Gago (2020, np), “the strike becomes a specific device to politicize violence against women and feminized bodies because it links them to the violence of contemporary capitalist accumulation”; and, precisely because of their insubordination to the rules of the capitalist game and the protagonism attributed in this environment of strike to women – who are the engine of the economy both in the domestic and commercial spheres –, that the mobilization of social struggles becomes relevant, being the strike “a way of blocking the continuity of capital production” (GAGO, 2020, np) and, at the same time, a driver of public policies aimed at mitigating the violence denounced by women in this area of struggle. It is in this context that the Argentine decree is sanctioned.

If, on the one hand, such mobilizations promoted the strengthening of traditional feminist activities, through assemblies of organizations, feminist, union and social activists (AGUIAR; ROJAS, 2020), on the other hand, social networks have also become privileged places for discursive exchanges and organization of social mobilization (ACOSTA, 2020).

In this context, it is noteworthy that the Argentine feminist movements have contributed significantly in the search for greater equality and for a different model of organization of society, including, through proposals that echoed in the Interministerial Board of Care Policies and that in the sphere of academic, have also found support in discussions of Feminist Economics.

GENDER AND FEMINIST ECONOMY CHAINS

Pérez Orozco (2005) starts from the premise that economics was a field of knowledge created by men to explain male experiences. This argument was built on the foundations already paved by Nelson's (1995) criticism, inspired by feminist social movements. The context of the insertion of feminist theory in the economic sciences, to the economic model of the traditional economy, homo economicus – based on the shipwrecked Robinson Crusoe, a character from a novel dating from the 1700s, who, isolated on an island, makes decisions without interacting with other elements of society; the prioritization of “hard” methods – related to exact calculations –, to the detriment of “soft” methods – characterized by the use of historical, social and empirical data; the topics considered 012 economic, and consequently those that are neglected by classical contributions, such as mercantile work and domestic work, respectively, and; to traditional economic pedagogy, responsible for reinforcing these androcentric biases.

Therefore, the androcentric bias is present in traditional economics as the gender perspective is not contemplated, excluding, consequently, several aspects related to experiences considered “feminine” for the understanding of economic inequality – such as domestic work . In this context, feminist economic theorists (CARRASCO et al., 2011; RODRÍGUEZ ENRÍQUEZ, 2015; TEIXEIRA, 2018); question such assumptions, even defending that the Care Economy is one of the relevant economic engines as a whole. In this sense, they defend the need to formulate public policies to mitigate disparities, as in the case of the Argentine Decree.

In this context, debates on the Feminist Economy advanced at different speeds and depths, according to the proposed degree of rupture with the androcentric bias. While there is a current that defends the visibility of women in current indicators and arrangements, there are

other currents that defend more significant changes. Next, essential aspects of each current identified by Pérez Orozco (2005) will be presented: Gender Economy, Feminist Economy of Reconciliation and Feminist Economy of Disruption and, finally, contextualization of the Care Economy in relation to the Feminist Economy and the Decree 475/2021 (ARGENTINA, 2021).

Gender Economics – or Neoclassical Feminist Theory

The term “gender” is usually defined in the literature as “the social meaning attributed to biological differences between the sexes” (FERBER; NELSON, 1993, p. 9 *apud* FERNANDEZ, 2018). Gender economics, therefore, analyzes economic models according to the incorporation – or not – of gender as an analytical category based on two main currents (PÉREZ OROZCO, 2005): equity studies, which analyze the causes of -female representation and erasure in the field of science, and feminist empiricism – which highlights the importance of rescuing female experiences to explain economic inequalities.

The Gender Economy is intrinsically linked to the traditional molds of neoclassical economic theory, differentiating itself, however, by imputing the gender focus to the same paradigms, a strategy named by Hewitson (1999 *apud* PÉREZ OROZCO, 2005) like “add women and modify”. However, as Robeyns (2000) argues, the current contribution can be reduced to the act of “counting women” or separating the figures according to sexual orientation, while maintaining the models, methods and topics, making the methodological framework used consist of, according to the author, in “playing the game by the boys rule”.

The Argentine Decree, by going beyond the mere identification that women are harmed in their retirement processes, presupposes that the identification suggested by the gender economy has already been carried out in previous stages, which allowed the identification, recognition and action to modify this reality. This is because, when adopting the neoclassical methodology, domestic work would need to be seen as "non-economic", and therefore not could be equated with paid work, belonging to the mercantile sphere.

Gender Economics – or Neoclassical Feminist Theory

According to Pérez Orozco (2005), the Feminist Economy of Reconciliation intends to redefine the fundamental concepts of economy and work, recovering the set of invisible female activities (condensed in domestic work) and combining this recovery with previous concepts and milestones. The author divides the recovery into four phases: the redefinition of the concept

of work and the inclusion of domestic work as an economic activity with a focus on measuring working time and on how it would be possible to compensate for the disparity (WARING, 1988 apud PÉREZ OROZCO , 2005); the visibility of unequal gender relations and domestic and market work being designated in a disparate way, attributed by the neoclassical model to the concept of traditional nuclear family where the man is the guarantor of resources and the woman, the housewife -, and opposed by feminist economists of conciliation with the concept of sexual division of labor. The third phase consists of analyzing the causes of the unequal division of income, which in neoclassical theories is attributed to gender roles affecting the economic position of men and women in commercial and domestic environments. Economists with a Marxist tendency, on the other hand, designate inequality as a consequence of the action of capitalism and patriarchy.

Finally, the category seeks to explain the economic activity of women in their reality, integrating the economic spheres of production, typically studied in androcentric currents, with that of reproduction, recovered by feminist theorists, thus demonstrating the dual presence of women in these spheres and the importance of this understanding for the formulation of social welfare processes (PÉREZ OROZCO, 2005).

It is possible to find alignment of the Argentine Decree with this current, in the sense that the proposed devices consider a certain transformation in the traditional economic perspectives, seeking to guarantee women, the visibility of those jobs previously assigned to the domestic scope and family care, with work activities in the market . That is, by considering motherhood as an activity that can be counted as working time, it inspires a redefinition of the very concept of work, also encompassing the definition of care used by Rodríguez Enríquez and Marzonetto (2016, p. 105) as “indispensable activities to satisfy people's basic reproduction needs, providing physical and symbolic elements that allow them to live in society”; and the Interministerial Board of Care Policies (2020, p. 22) by proposing “recognizing care as a need, work and right” and “properly remunerating people who engage in care in different social environments” reaffirms the concept of work intrinsic to the Economy of Care.

Feminist Breakthrough Economy

The Feminist Rupture Economy arises from the criticism grounded by Himmelweit (1995 apud PÉREZ OROZCO, 2005) that despite the addition of typically feminine economic activities to conciliation theories, the analysis center of the studies continues to be the mercantile, the masculine and the western (WOOD, 1997 apud PÉREZ OROZCO, 2005).

According to Pérez Orozco (2005), the object of analysis should not be production or the market, but the extent to which these elements collaborate or hinder the maintenance of life.

In this sense, the feminist economists of rupture start to focus the analysis on the processes of sustainability of human life:

This focus renounces the search for a unitary subject with a common experience and interests that define women in the world, recognizing the difference and power relations that are established between women themselves. For Carrasco, human needs are not limited to goods and services, but also to affections and relationships (2001:14). This means that values traditionally associated with women such as care, and which have always been on the periphery of economic analysis, must be revalued and recognized. From this point of view, the notion of work used to delimit the work carried out in the market needs to be expanded to incorporate all the activities that enter into the formation of part of the process of sustainability of human life. (TEIXEIRA, 2018, p. 159).

Despite the amendment to Argentine law aimed at repairing the gaps that led to the exclusion of women from the labor market – attributed to care activities performed at home and hitherto not taken into account for retirement –, the Decree does not establish terms that are of fact that transforms the mercantile and androcentric logic that dominates the economic system (PÉREZ OROZCO, 2005), and therefore cannot be fully classified as part of the category of Feminist Rupture Economy.

However, when the Decree is observed as inserted in the gender agenda of Argentine and global political and social organizations, in this context condensed in the feminist marches Ni Una Menos and Paro Internacional de Mujeres, it is possible to affirm that it is part of a global practice of promotion and defense of Human Rights, which claims (in addition to the end of gender violence, menstrual equity, legal abortion, remuneration for domestic tasks, sexual education against homophobia and transphobia and parity in labor remuneration), the end of the logic of exploitation of heterosexual patriarchy – therefore, it can be seen as an achievement of the feminist movement in Argentina, which finds some support in the proposal of the Feminist Economy of Disruption.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

This work aimed to investigate the case of Argentine Decree 475/2021, which recognizes maternal care as a contribution time for retirement, within the scope of the growing debate on Feminist Economy. The Feminist Economy establishes a debate relevant to the work of care and its inclusion in the global agenda of Human Rights and gender through the

establishment of public policy recommendations aimed at investing in national care delivery systems, eradicating poverty and extreme wealth, protection of caregivers' rights and guarantee of living wages and influence in decision-making processes, valuing care in business policies and practices, in addition to challenging sexist – or androcentric – norms and beliefs.

From the categories developed by Pérez Orozco (2005), it is possible to consider that the Argentine Decree falls under the scope of the Feminist Economy of Conciliation, as it proposes changes only for certain groups – those of women with children, more specifically –, when in Indeed, the theoretical framework of the Care Economy recognizes that invisible domestic work does not only take place around caring for children and the elderly, but around the entire family nucleus in the domestic environment, being essential for the functioning of the market, and making thus part of the economy.

Although Care Retirement is within the scope of changes centered on policies to reconcile work and family life – equivalent to the Feminist Economy of Reconciliation –, the Care Economy involves broader aspects that must be taken into account and prioritized by formulators of care. public policies in different spheres taking into account the maximization of gender disparities and human rights violations in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic.

Although the Argentine Decree, in itself, does not represent a break with androcentric precepts and traditional economics, the movement that strongly influenced its creation and approval aims to reach this level. Therefore, the Decree cannot be observed in isolation, but rather as a public policy that represents a step in the constitution of rights claimed by a world women's movement through the construction of knowledge and action and political struggle for Human Rights.

It is important to consider that the approval of the Decree is a recent action, whose reverberations could not yet be fully observed, and whose interaction with the categories proposed here may change throughout its implementation. It is also important to point out that Argentina exerts influence over the other countries in the region, and the sanction of this decree could serve as a model for more countries to turn their legislation towards gender perspectives on care, reinforcing the global meaning of the propositions generated by the agenda of gender in the context of human rights.

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